

Stabilities of Bivalent Metal Chelates of 3-Hydroxy-3-phenyl-1-*p*-acetylphenyltriazene

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Stabilities of palladium, copper, nickel, zinc, and manganese chelates of 3-hydroxy-3-phenyl-1-*p*-acetylphenyltriazene have been determined in 70% v/v dioxane-water mixture by employing the Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique. The titration medium has been maintained at a constant ionic strength (0.1 M, KCl) and at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$. Log *K*: palladium 21.511, copper 21.160, nickel 15.937, zinc 14.239, and manganese 10.895.

A new class of chelating agents, possessing functional grouping $-N(OH)N=N-$, has been recently introduced by Sogani *et al.*¹⁻³. The parent compound of the series, 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene, has been reported as a highly selective reagent for palladium⁴ and copper². The sulphonic acid derivative, 3-hydroxy-3-phenyl-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyltriazene, is water-soluble and furnishes water-soluble complexes. It has been reported as a very good reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium⁶, molybdenum⁷, and iron⁸.

Substitution of different groups at different positions of the aryl nuclei of the parent compound influences the stabilities of the resulting metal chelates. The present investigation deals with the determination of stabilities of bivalent metal chelates of *para*-acetyl-substituted hydroxytriazene, namely, 3-hydroxy-3-phenyl-1-*p*-acetylphenyltriazene, in 70% v/v dioxane-water mixture by employing Calvin and Molchior's method⁹, commonly referred as the Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique. Titrations were carried out in duplicates, using 40:1 ratio of the ligand to metal-ion concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Hydroxy-3-phenyl-1-*p*-acetylphenyltriazene was prepared by employing the method given by Sogani *et al.*¹¹. A weighed amount of this compound was dissolved in 70% v/v dioxane-water mixture and diluted to provide a 0.04 M solution.

Analytical grades of palladium chloride, copper chloride, nickel sulphate, zinc oxide, and manganese sulphate were used for preparing standard solutions. After standardising these solutions by the usual classical methods, these were diluted to furnish 0.002 M solutions.

1. Sogani and Bhattacharya, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 81.
2. *Idem, ibid.*, 1956, **28**, 1816.
3. *Idem, this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 563.
4. Jain, Gupta, and Sogani, *ibid.*, 1960, **37**, 531.
5. Gupta and Sogani, *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 771.
6. Sogani and Bhattacharya, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **29**, 397.
7. *Idem, ibid.*, 1961, **33**, 1273.
8. Gupta and Sogani, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 97.
9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.

Approximately 0.1*N* carbonate-free sodium hydroxide was prepared and standardised with analytical grade potassium hydrogen phthalate. It was diluted to give 0.02*M* solution. The B. D. H. dioxane was purified by Weissberger's method¹⁰.

Potentiometric Titrations.—The *pH*-titrations of ligands with a standard alkali solution in absence and in presence of different metal ions were carried out by using a Cambridge bench-type *pH*-meter which provided values accurate to 0.01 *pH* unit. The *pH*-meter was standardised before, and checked after, each titration with buffer solutions of *pH* 4.0 and 9.2. Electrode system consisted of glass electrode (*pH* range 1-13) and a reference saturated calomel electrode.

0.04*M* Ligand solution (10 ml) in 70% v/v dioxane-water mixture was pipetted in a titration vessel. A sufficient amount of 0.02*M* nitric acid was added to it to lower the *pH* to about 2. Final ionic concentration was maintained at 0.1*M* by adding 2.5 ml of 2*M* -KCl. When titrating in presence of metal ions, a 2×10^{-3} *M* metal solution (5ml) was added at this stage. The total volume of the contents was made to 50 ml by adding varying amounts of dioxane and distilled water in such proportions that it finally became 70% v/v dioxane-water mixture. It was titrated against 0.02*M* -NaOH. The temperature of the solution throughout the titration was maintained at $25^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. The *pH*-meter readings, obtained at a given alkali addition in duplicate titrations, were reproducible with a maximum variation of ± 0.01 *pH* unit. The titration curves are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

FIG. 1

The horizontal distance between the reference titration curve and the curve obtained in presence of a metal ion supplies the amount of metal-bound ligand. This value, divided by the total metal-ion concentration, provides the value for $\bar{n}$. In this way the values of $\bar{n}$ at different pH values were calculated.

At any pH, the value of free ligand-ion concentration, $[T]$, was calculated from the total ligand concentration, $[HT]$, and its dissociation quotient. This is based on the assumption that the amount of chelating agent over metal ion is so great that removal of H^+ by chelation does not cause any significant change in the equilibrium: $HT \rightleftharpoons H^+ + T^-$. The pK value of 3-hydroxy-3-phenyl-1-*p*-acetylphenyltriazone has been determined spectrophotometrically¹¹ as 10.962.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

In calculating the values for $\bar{n}$ and $[T]$, the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume, produced by addition of alkali during titrations. In this way, a series of values for $\bar{n}$ and $[T]$, corresponding to different pH values, was obtained. The results are shown in Table I. The formation curves for metal chelates of 3-hydroxy-3-phenyl-1-*p*-acetylphenyltriazone are shown in Fig. 3. The values for $\log k_1$, $\log k_2$, and $\log K_{av}$ ($\frac{1}{2} \log K$) for different metal chelates were read directly from the formation curves. The values are recorded in Table II.

DISCUSSION

The consumption of alkali during the course of titration can be due to the ligand, the hydrolysis of metal ion, and the ligand protons liberated in complex formation.

The ligand under study is a very weak acid (pK 10.962). Thus, the ligand proton as such is not in a titratable form. Hydrolysis of these metal ions has been studied in 70% v/v dioxane-water mixture¹¹. The pH for $\bar{n}=1.5$ in all the cases is lower than the pH at which the hydrolysis of these metal ions starts. Hence hydrolysis of these metal ions does not interfere in the stability measurements. Moreover, there was no precipitation during chelation titrations, clearly ruling out the possibility of hydrolysis of these metal ions in presence of a large excess of the ligand.

11. Purohit, Ph. D. Thesis, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, 1963.

TABLE I
 Formation curve data for metal chelates.

Palladium.		Copper.		Nickel.		Zinc.		Manganese.	
pH.	$\bar{n}$.	pH.	$\bar{n}$.	pH.	$\bar{n}$.	pH.	$\bar{n}$.	pH.	$\bar{n}$.
	$p[T]$.		$p(T)$.		$p(T)$.		$p(T)$.		$p(T)$.
2.05	0.40	2.10	0.35	4.10	0.28	4.90	0.21	6.75	0.28
	11.019		10.968		8.990		8.190		6.432
2.10	0.50	2.20	0.55	4.30	0.50	5.15	0.38	7.00	0.50
	10.972		10.872		8.791		7.941		6.094
2.15	0.70	2.30	0.90	4.50	0.78	5.30	0.50	7.25	0.70
	10.925		10.770		8.592		7.792		5.845
2.30	1.00	2.40	1.15	5.00	1.00	5.40	0.62	7.75	1.00
	10.780		10.080		8.094		7.602		5.346
2.40	1.30	2.55	1.25	5.40	1.15	5.65	0.87	8.20	1.30
	10.684		10.534		7.694		7.444		4.900
2.55	1.50	2.75	1.40	5.95	1.50	5.95	1.08	8.30	1.50
	10.539		10.338		7.146		7.145		4.801
2.70	1.60	3.05	1.72	6.10	1.65	6.15	1.22	8.65	1.75
	10.392		10.042		6.997		6.946		4.458
2.95	1.72	3.50	1.95	6.20	1.75	6.50	1.45	8.75	1.80
	10.146		9.590		6.898		6.597		4.314
3.15	1.90	3.65	2.00	6.50	1.95	6.65	1.50	8.96	2.00
	9.949		9.446		6.599		6.447		4.148
3.25	2.00			7.75	2.00	7.10	1.78		
	9.860				6.350		5.999		
						7.40	1.93		
							2.00		
						7.50			

Thus, the consumption of an excess of alkali in chelation titration over the simple ligand titration is due to ligand protons liberated during complex formation. This may be represented as:

The order of stability of hydroxytriazone-metal chelates has been found as: palladium > copper > nickel > zinc > manganese.

TABLE II

Stability constants of metal chelates,

Metal ion.	Log k_1 .	Log k_2 .	Log K_{av} .	Log $k_1 k_2$.
Palladium	10.972	10.539	10.780	21.511
Copper	10.910	10.250	10.720	21.160
Nickel	8.791	7.146	8.094	15.937
Zinc	7.792	6.447	7.230	14.239
Manganese	6.094	4.801	5.346	10.895

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